

EcoPlastic

Eco conversion of lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste into high performing biopolymers.

D6.7 SECOND ANNUAL REPORT ON DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

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Abbreviation list

(A-Z)

AVE – Avecom, Belgium

DEC – Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication

DECP – Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Plan

IMGGE – Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, Serbia

KPI – Key Performance Indicator

KTH – Kungliga Tekniska Hoegskolan, *i.e.*, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden

NL - Newsletter

NOVA – Associação para a Inovação e Desenvolvimento da FCT, *i.e.*, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Portugal

TUS – Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest, Ireland

Y1 – First year of the EcoPlastiC project

Y2 – Second year of the EcoPlastiC project

Y3 – Third year of the EcoPlastiC project

1. Executive summary

This deliverable provides a detailed report on the progress towards the implementation of the dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy, designed and defined in the first year of the EcoPlastiC project. General framework for implementation of these activities was previously described in the deliverable **D6.1** Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan (M6) and was updated in the deliverable **D6.3** First annual report on dissemination, exploitation and communication activities (M12).

The report **D6.7** gives overview of the key dissemination and communication activities during the second year of the EcoPlastiC project (1 October 2023 – 30 September 2024) and focuses on the main key performance indicators defined in the DEC plan. It summaries the main activities of all partners, including development of new dissemination materials, presence at industry events, conferences and symposia, project advertisement in the media, published results from the project, visits to schools and project promotion to the public, as well as a successful EcoPlastiC newsletter campaign. Each activity has been put against initial targets and indicators in the Table 13 in Chapter 4 to measure success of the actions taken so far (M24 of EcoPlastiC project). Our exploitation progress has been updated by all EcoPlastiC partners and is presented in the Annex I (Tables 15-18).

In the second year of the EcoPlastiC project, which surpassed the successes of the first year, we significantly advanced our efforts to engage stakeholders and expand the project's reach to a broader audience. Building on the foundation established in the first year, we not only strengthened awareness of the project's objectives and activities, but also enhanced the visibility for our project team and partners. As a result, the majority of the activities outlined in the DEC plan have been successfully executed.

2. Introduction

EcoPlastiC started in October 2022 as a 3-year Horizon Europe Pathfinder programme project funded by the EC and EIC. Its Consortium involves five partners from four EU countries (TUS from Ireland, AVE from Belgium, NOVA from Portugal and KTH from Sweden) and one associated country (IMGGE from Serbia), and four partners, namely TUS, NOVA, IMGGE and KTH are research institutions and AVE is a Small to Medium sized Enterprise (SME).

EcoPlastiC aims to offer an efficient solution to the widespread issue of PET plastic pollution by transforming it into eco-friendly plastic prototypes, specifically high-performance bioplastics. The project focuses on converting lower-grade PET and mixed, resistant PET plastic waste into advanced biopolymers, directing this waste into eco-products that can be continuously recycled in a bio-loop. These innovative eco-plastics and products are designed as drop-in alternatives, enabling smooth integration into industrial processes and easy adoption by consumers.

The DEC Plan (D6.1) described in detail the approach to and planning for communication and dissemination of EcoPlastiC project and the project results. The Y1 report (D6.3) represented an update of the DEC Plan and it summarised all activities taken by the EcoPlastiC partners to fulfil project's objectives. In Y2, we aimed to bring the project even closer to all stakeholders, to participate in science and industry events and to develop and strengthen collaboration and information exchange between similar EU-funded projects.

3. Communication strategy

We previously reported the development of the visual identity materials, such as EcoPlastiC logo, the watermark for official documents (such as minutes, conference reports *etc.*) and the Power Point presentation template. We also reported on the printed materials that were developed within the Y1 of the project: EcoPlastiC brochure and 3 versions of the roll up.

3.1. Dissemination materials in Y2

During Y2 of the project, other visual elements and promotional materials were developed. All mentioned materials were created to match the visual identity of the website and the overall project design concept. They are available for download at the EcoPlastiC website:

<https://ecoplasticproject.eu/download>

3.1.1. Bookmark

The bookmark features a vertical circular process diagram on the left side, set against a background of white PET plastic granules. The diagram includes the following elements from top to bottom:

- EcoPlastiC logo** and tagline: "Putting PET plastics into a personal, responsible loop".
- Recycling products**: A circular arrow icon with a bottle and a can.
- PHA**: A circular icon with a mesh pattern.
- Virgin biodegradable extraction**: A vertical arrow pointing upwards.
- Bioprocess identification**: A circular icon with a microscope.
- Enzymes & Microbes**: A circular icon with a cluster of microbes.
- Bioprocess identification**: A circular icon with a plant growing in a field.
- Recycling products**: A circular icon with a recycling symbol.

On the right side of the bookmark, the following logos are displayed:

- TUS**
- NVAO**
- Avecom**
- 2000** (with a circular logo)
- KTH** (with a circular logo)
- A **QR code**.
- Funded by the European Union** and **European Innovation Council** logos.
- Text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe EIC Pathfinder programme under grant agreement number 101046758".

3.1.2. Notepad

The notepad is divided into three vertical sections against a background of white PET plastic granules:

- Left section:** Features the **EcoPlastiC** logo.
- Middle section:** A large area with horizontal lines for writing.
- Right section:** Contains logos for **TUS**, **Avecom**, **NVAO**, **2000**, and **KTH**, along with the **Funded by the European Union** and **European Innovation Council** logos. At the bottom, it includes the text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe EIC Pathfinder programme under grant agreement number 101046758".

3.1.3. Folder

3.1.4. Ballpoint pens

3.2. Channels

For appropriate communication and dissemination to all target groups, EcoPlastiC team uses different channels providing information through a variety of formats. The summary and comparison between activities in Y1 (**Table 1**) and Y2 (**Table 2**) is shown.

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Table 1 - Indicators and targets for the website and social media on 30/09/2023 (Y1).

Activity Y1	Indicator (Audience)	Target number	Numbers (Activity)
Website	1700 unique visitors	Visits per year: <500 poor 500-1000 good >1000 excellent	16 news
X/Twitter	169 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	53 posts + 9 reposts
LinkedIn	104 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	54 posts + 2 reposts
Facebook	24 followers + 15 likes	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	50 posts + 1 reposts
Instagram	166 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	26 posts
Newsletter	211 subscribers	4 campaigns	1 campaign

Table 2 - Indicators and targets for the website and social media on 27/09/2024 (Y2).

Activity Y2	Indicator (Audience)	Target number	Numbers (Activity)
Website	3600 unique visitors	Visits per year: <500 poor 500-1000 good >1000 excellent	40 news
X/Twitter	356 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	119 posts + 14 reposts
LinkedIn	362 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	123 posts + 4 reposts

Facebook	38 followers + 19 likes	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	119 posts + 6 reposts
Instagram	280 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	80 posts
Newsletter	218 subscribers	4 campaigns	2 campaign

More details on the website analytics and updates (3.2.1 and 3.2.2, respectively), the social media accounts and campaigns (3.2.3 and 3.2.4, respectively) and the newsletter (3.2.5) are provided below.

3.2.1. EcoPlastiC Y2 website analytics

The primary source of information about the project is the EcoPlastiC website, created and administrated by IMGGE (www.ecoplasticproject.eu) and it is one of the most relevant dissemination tools for reaching the largest audience possible, including the scientific community, the project’s stakeholders, relevant industries, but also the wider public.

We use the [Plausible](#) to study web analytics, and the report for the past 12 months (made on Friday, 27/09/2024) is shown below (also available at this [link](#)):

All 5 partner countries (1st place Serbia, 2nd place Ireland, 4th place Portugal, 6th place Sweden, and 9th place Belgium) are in the Top 10 countries that visited the website (on Wednesday, 11/09/2024):

Country	Visitors ↓	%
Serbia	1.2k	34.1
Ireland	303	8.2
United States	268	7.3
Portugal	174	4.7
Netherlands	161	4.4
Sweden	136	3.7
Germany	121	3.3
India	117	3.2
Belgium	115	3.1
France	113	3.1

All EcoPlastiC social media pages (3rd place LinkedIn, 5th place Facebook, 8th place Instagram, 9th place Twitter) are in the Top 10 sources that lead the visitors to the website (on Thursday, 11/09/2024):

Source	Visitors ↓	Bounce Rate	Visit Duration
Direct / None	1.8k	57%	2m 56s
Google	1k	60%	1m 21s
LinkedIn	222	69%	50s
imgge.bg.ac.rs	132	64%	2m 08s
Facebook	86	70%	28s
Bing	67	46%	1m 55s
afjfyggfe	43	19%	1s
Instagram	42	63%	1m 08s
Twitter	39	65%	1m 11s
newsletter	38	66%	46s

3.2.2. EcoPlastiC website updates

The [Home page](#) was enriched by adding the short promotional video that explains the EcoPlastiC project to the visitor: https://youtu.be/A_AZzEyYoXs

The [News page](#) is where we post about the project's activities and events, and this page has already become the most dynamic and vast part of the website. There are 42 news (as on 27/09/2024). During Y2, we made it possible to search the news more easily using a search filter that organises them based on the project year.

The [Downloads page](#) contains all relevant downloadable materials and in Y2, we added all published papers and made them publicly available, as well as the Newsletters. The user interface now contains a filter that facilitates finding the desired category of downloads. In addition, all EcoPlastiC innovations published on the Innovation Radar are also available. The innovations were also emphasized as news: <https://ecoplasticproject.eu/posts/ecoplastic-innovations-on-the-innovation-radar>

3.2.3. Social media accounts

The EcoPlastiC project has social media accounts on X (Twitter), LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram. In Y2 of the project, the social media strategy continued to build on the foundation

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set in Y1. We aimed to further engage our audience by not only highlighting the teams and team leaders, but also by providing updates on meetings and ongoing activities such as event and conference participation.

Additionally, our posts explored broader topics related to the circular economy and sustainability. By doing so, we sought to create a more comprehensive narrative that linked various initiatives and projects, thereby attracting even greater interest from our audience.

X (formerly Twitter): @_EcoPlastiC_
<https://twitter.com/EcoPlastiC>

LinkedIn (company page): EcoPlastiC
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/ecoplastic-project/>

Facebook page: Ecoplastic
<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100088412644481>

Instagram: @ecoplastic_project

https://www.instagram.com/ecoplastic_project/

ecoplastic_project

Edit profile

View archive

80 posts

280 followers

167 following

EcoPlastiC project

Putting PET plastics into a perpetual bio-cyclable loop, European Innovation Council and Horizon Europe grant No... more

3.2.4. Social media campaigns

To ensure clear and consistent communication and dissemination with target groups, different types of communication formats have been developed and presented as part of social media campaigns.

3.2.4.1. Short video testimonials by Team Leaders

During Y1 of the project, we posted three out of five short video testimonials by the EcoPlastiC Team Leaders and the remaining two were posted in Y2. The Team Leaders presented themselves, their respective institutions and the role they play in the realisation of the EcoPlastiC project.

Y1

Margaret Brennan Fournet,
TUS

on 21/06/2023

Kim Windey,
AVE

on 25/07/2023

Filomena Freitas,
NOVA

on 26/09/2023

Y2

Mikael Hedenqvist, KTH

on 25/10/2023

Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic, IMGGE

on 22/11/2023

3.2.4.2. Presentation of all consortium teams

During Y2 of the project all teams and team members of the consortium were presented in a promotional campaign. From the 39 consortium members, the male to female ratio is 11:28, showing that 70% of the team are women and underscoring the project's efforts on promoting women's participation in STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics):

IMGGE team

on 09/08/2024

KTH team

on 16/08/2024

NOVA team

on 23/08/2024

AVE team

on 30/08/2024

TUS team

on 10/09/2024

3.2.5. Newsletters

As stated in the DEC plan, during the lifetime of the project, four electronic newsletters will be prepared and distributed to the project target groups, project partners, networks and posted on website.

We previously reported that NL#1 was released in M10 (July 2023) to an audience of 191 subscribers and it is available on the Downloads page of the EcoPlastiC website, as well as online at the following link:

<https://preview.mailerlite.io/emails/webview/357939/94755400200488336>

The NL#2 was released in M19 (April 2024) to an audience of 213 subscribers and it is available on the Downloads page of the EcoPlastiC website, as well as online at the following link:

<https://preview.mailerlite.io/emails/webview/357939/117664918347449489>

Each Newsletter contains the following sections: Introduction, EcoPlastiC partners, EcoPlastiC research highlights, EcoPlastiC @ events, EcoPlastiC in the media, EcoPlastiC publications and the Contact section.

3.3. Activities in Y2

The summary of EcoPlastiC activities and their comparison between Y1 (**Table 3**) and Y2 (**Table 4**) are shown, with indicators and targets clearly explained.

Table 3 – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and targets for EcoPlastiC activities in **Y1** on 30/09/2023.

Activity Y1	Indicator (Audience)	Target number	Numbers (Activity)
Events	Number of events attendances	Attendances: <5 poor 5-7 good >7 excellent	7 events attended
Conferences	Number of conferences, symposia, and workshops attendances	Attendances: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	6 conferences attended
Publications	Number of articles published	Published articles: <5 poor 5-10 good >10 excellent	1 publication
Media releases	Number of media	Media: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	5 media releases
Education and public engagement at partners institutes	Number of engagements	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	0
School visits	Number of visits	Visits: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	0
Women in Science events	Number of events attendances	Attendances: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	0

Special sessions, forums, events organised by other EU Research Initiatives	Number of events engagement	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	1 visit
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Table 4 – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and targets for the EcoPlastiC activities in Y2 on 27/09/2024.

Activity Y2	Indicator (Audience)	Target number	Numbers (Activity)
Events	Number of events attendances	Attendances: <5 poor 5-7 good >7 excellent	14 events attended
Conferences	Number of conferences, symposia, and workshops attendances	Attendances: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	12 conferences attended
Publications	Number of articles published	Published articles: <5 poor 5-10 good >10 excellent	6 publications
Media releases	Number of media	Media: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	9 media releases
Education and public engagement at partners' institutes	Number of engagements	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	3 lectures/visits
School visits	Number of visits	Visits: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	16 visits
Women in Science events	Number of events attendances	Attendances: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	1

Special sessions, forums, events organised by other EU Research Initiatives	Number of events engagement	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	3 visits
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More details on the attended events (3.3.1), conferences (3.3.2), publications (3.3.3), media releases (3.3.4), education and public engagement (3.3.5), school visits (3.3.6), women in science events (3.3.7) and special sessions, forums, events organised by other EU Research Initiatives (3.3.8) are provided below.

3.3.1. Events

During Y2, the project partners represented EcoPlastiC at 14 events across Europe and their list is presented in **Table 5**, while a photo from the event (where applicable) together with a short description is also provided below **Table 5**.

Table 5 – List of events from Y2 where the EcoPlastiC project was presented.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	The New Food Paradigm	AVE	Exhibitor	EcoPlastiC project	04/10/2023	Paris, France	200
2	Aquarama Trade Fair	AVE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	19/10/2023	Leuven, Belgium	1250
3	Green chemistry for a circular economy and a sustainable future	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	02/11/2023	Belgrade, Serbia	55
4	Avecom webinar	AVE	Organiser and presenter	EcoPlastiC project	14/11/2024	online	83
5	Trends in Environmental Biotechnology	AVE	Presenter	Sustainable solutions for environmental recovery and side stream valorization	22/11/2023	online	61
6	Seminar in Clausthal	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	22/11/2023	Clausthal, Germany	30
7	ANSO Project Seminar on "Bioplastics Upcycling Loop"	TUS	Presenter	Achieving Sustainable Plastics to Live Within Our	14/12/2023	online	50

				Planetary Boundaries			
8	Annual Polymer Conference (APC)	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	18/04/2024	Athlone, Ireland	200
9	66 th International Fair of Technics and Technical Achievements	IMGGE	Exhibitor	EcoPlastiC project	21-24/05/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	19.047
10	60 th Meeting of the Serbian Chemical Society	IMGGE	Panellist	EcoPlastiC project	08-09/06/2024	Nis, Serbia	40
11	Science, Systems and Programs Work Stream Sessions – GO!PHA	IMGGE	Speaker	Closing the Loop: Transforming Waste Plastics into advances Biomaterials for a circular Economy	20/06/2024	online	25
12	European Researchers' Night	IMGGE	Speaker	EcoPlastiC project - from plastic waste to sustainable biopolymers	24/09/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	30
13	European Researchers' Night	IMGGE	Exhibitor	EcoPlastiC - Discovering the future of plastics	27/09/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	180
14	European Researchers' Night	NOVA	Exhibitor	Bioeconomy in action: transforming wastes into valuable products	27/09/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	220

1. The New Food Paradigm

AVE had a booth at The New Food Paradigm in Paris. At this event the most forward thinking startups in alternative protein, new ingredients and enabling technologies were brought together with the industry stakeholders and investors who have the resources to scale their innovations. AVE distributed flyers of EcoPlastiC. Stijn Boeren attended the event.

2. Aquarama Trade Fair

AVE was an exhibitor at the Aquarama trade fair & conference. A prominent expo and conference focusing on water technology and treatment, this event was a key gathering for industry professionals and water sector enthusiasts. Kim Windey attended the event and EcoPlastiC brochures were distributed.

3. Green chemistry for a circular economy and a sustainable future

In November 2023, experts in the fields of environmental protection, innovation, economics, economy and science gathered to discuss key issues related to the application of green chemistry and sustainable chemical processes in achieving the circular economy. This hybrid event had over 80 in-person and online participants and included lectures on innovative products and processes that support the circular economy and contribute to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. Within the session "Green Chemistry as a Support to the Economy towards Sustainable Development – Examples of Good Practice", representatives of companies and science presented various innovations and good practices in the application of the principles of green chemistry. Dr Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic (IMGGE) attended the event .

4. AVEcom webinar

Under the name "Unveiling the Role of Biodegradation in a Circular Economy" AVE organised a webinar designed to explore the vast potential of biodegradation in environmental remediation and discover AVE's biopolymerization processes for high-performance, biobased and biodegradable polymers. The EcoPlastiC project was also presented by the Project Ambassador Helena Koninckx (AVE), including the ways for combating single-use plastic pollution, presenting eco-friendly alternatives that not only reduce waste, but also offer sustainable solutions to conventional plastics.

5. Trends in Environmental Biotechnology

AVE, presented by Michael Pil, has given a presentation at an online seminar with as topic Trends in Environmental Biotechnology. The presentation was about sustainable solutions for environmental recovery and side stream valorization. In the presentation the EcoPlastiC project was given as an illustration of a biofermentation towards biopolymers.

6. Seminar in Clausthal

EcoPlastiC project was presented at the internal monthly seminar of the Technical University of Clausthal (Germany). Marijana Ponjavic (IMGGE) attended the event.

7. ANSO Project Seminar on "Bioplastics Upcycling Loop"

Margaret Brennan Fournet (TUS) presented the topic "Achieving the sustainable plastics to live within our planetary boundaries".

8. Annual Polymer Conference (APC)

APC Conference brings together Irish and International industry plastics leaders, engineers and scientists to discuss the latest developments and challenges facing the industry through a mix of networking, expert talks and interactive industry displays. Dr Margaret Brennan Fournet (TUS) attended the event.

9. 66th International Fair of Technics and Technical Achievements

International Fair of Technics and Technical Achievements is a traditional meeting and business contact point, which enables numerous exhibitors and visitors to satisfy their business expectations. This is the most important economic and technological event in Serbia and the South East Europe. IMGGE was one of 904 exhibitors at this event. New technologies and technological achievements were presented, as well as global development paths and trends, including the EcoPlastiC project.

10. 60th Meeting of the Serbian Chemical Society

IMGGE was invited to take part in the panel discussion "Green Chemistry – Activities and Challenges" where the EcoPlastiC project was presented by Marijana Ponjavic. This lively and engaging discussion was part of the activities of the "Global Greenchem Innovation & Network Programme", which is implemented in Serbia in cooperation with the Yale University, USA.

11. Science, Systems and Programs Work Stream Sessions – GO!PHA

Science, Systems, and Programs Workstream are incredibly valuable, each month featuring two esteemed speakers who share their expert insights. Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic (IMGGE) attended the event and gave a talk "Closing the Loop: Transforming Waste Plastics into advanced Biomaterials for a circular Economy".

12. European Researchers' Night - Lecture in Belgrade

As part of the event before the great scientific adventure within the European Researchers' Night, lectures on very current and socially useful topics such as climate change, alternative ways of producing oxygen such as liquid wood, and how to use plastic waste to obtain sustainable biopolymers. Dr Brana Pantelic (IMGGE) attended the event and gave a talk "EcoPlastiC project - from plastic waste to sustainable biopolymers".

13. European Researchers' Night in Serbia

"Have you ever thought about how plastic can be sustainable? Have you already had the opportunity to explore concepts such as plastic recycling, the production and application of bioplastics, as well as the role of microorganisms in the process of breaking down plastic waste? If you are, or even if you are not, "EcoPlastiC" is here to bring you these exciting principles. Through a series of interactive activities, we will reveal details about mechanical processing of plastic waste, biological treatment of plastics, toxicity research of different molecules and bioplastic production techniques. Our goal is to inspire you and encourage you to think about plastic as the material of the future. And then... the direction under the microscope! We will breathe life into this concept with the help of the model organism *Caenorhabditis elegans* and explore bioplastics as an amazing material.

We invite you to join us and learn together how science can transform the way we look at plastic and its impact on the environment!"

14. European Researchers' Night in Serbia in Portugal

"Have you ever thought about all the "waste" that is generated daily on our planet? However, some of these discarded products can be turned into valuable items. This is called the Circular Bioeconomy. To achieve this, we can rely on the help of microorganisms to transform these residues into products like biopolymers, bioplastics, biofuels and biofertilizers. These products are valuable because they help to solve environmental problems and contribute to a sustainable future. By visiting our activity, you will be able to see examples of these products, learn about the production process, and participate in a hands-on activity where biopolymer spheres, emulsions, and more will be made. Come explore, learn, and get hands-on with us! Together, we can make a difference and promote a more sustainable world. We look forward to see you!"

3.3.2. Conferences

During Y2, the results from the EcoPlastiC project were presented in 7 scientific conferences through 12 scientific contributions, including plenary lectures, invited lectures and poster and oral presentations. The list of conferences is presented in **Table 6**, while a photo from the event (where applicable) together with a short description is provided below **Table 6**.

Table 6 – List of scientific conferences in Y2 where the EcoPlastiC project results were presented.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	2 nd Congress of Molecular Biologists of Serbia - CoMBoS2	IMGGE	Plenary Lecturer	Microbes and microbial enzymes for degradation of (bio)plastics	06-08/10/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	155
2		IMGGE	Invited Speaker	Bacterial nanocellulose – new beginning for end-of-life plastics			
3	10 th International Conference	IMGGE	Plenary Lecturer	Waste to value: From bugs to drugs	30/11-02/12/2024	Larissa, Greece	240
4	Mikrobiokomsos - MIKROBIOKOSMOS 2023	NOVA	Presenter (poster)	Bioconversion of unrecyclable PET waste into biodegradable polyhydroxyalkanoates by a newly isolated <i>Delftia tsuruhatensis</i> strain			
5		IMGGE	Presenter (poster)	Conversion of mixed plastic waste containing PET into biopolymer bacterial nanocellulose			
6		TUS	Presenter (poster)	Exploring the enzymatic ability of strains isolated from plastic polluted environments for enhancing synthetic and natural biopolymers' biodegradation			
7		TUS	Presenter (poster)	Biocompatible eco-plastic blends with enhanced antimicrobial activity by addition of essential oils			

8	#RSCPoster	TUS	Presenter (poster)	Sustainable Route for Mixed (Petro-Bio)Plastic Waste Valorisation via Synergy-Promoted Enzymatic Depolymerization	05-06/03/2024	online	1700 delegates from over 80 countries
9	3Bs Materials International Conference	NOVA	Keynote speaker	Microbial polymers: novel biomaterials with improved properties	06-08/03/2024	Seville, Spain	160
10	EFB virtual conference	TUS	Speaker	Biotechnological Treatment of Polyethylene Terephthalate Mixed Plastic Streams	20/03/2024	online	70-80
11	13 th Congress of Microbiologists of Serbia	IMGGE	Invited Speaker	From soil to lab: Exploring toxicology with <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	04-06/04/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	180
12	6 th Symposium of Biotransformations for Pharmaceutical and Cosmetic Industry	IMGGE	Invited Speaker	Biotransforming waste streams into biomolecules and biomaterials	17-19/06/2024	Krakov, Poland	90

1-2. 2nd Congress of Molecular Biologists of Serbia - CoMBos2

CoMBos2 included 4 main Plenary Lectures, 18 Session Plenary Lectures and 18 Invited Lectures, as well as 24 abstracts submitted by students (Bachelor, Master and PhD) and 91 abstracts from early career researchers (Postdocs).

Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic (IMGGE) was the Plenary Lecturer and delivered a presentation “Microbes and microbial enzymes for degradation of (bio)plastics”.

Sanja Jeremic (IMGGE) was an Invited Speaker and delivered a presentation “Bacterial nanocellulose – new beginning for end-of-life plastics”.

3-7. 10th International Conference Mikrobiokomsos

There were 9 Plenary lectures, 60 oral presentations and 170 poster presentations as part of the conference, from the research topics of Agriculture/Fisheries, Emerging approaches in

Microbiology, Environment, Systems Biology, One health/omics, Food/Nutrition, Bioengineering/Biotechnology.

Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic (IMGGE) was the Plenary Lecturer and delivered a presentation “Waste to value: From bugs to drugs”.

Patrícia Concórdio-Reis (NOVA) had a poster presentation titled “Bioconversion of unrecyclable PET waste into biodegradable polyhydroxyalkanoates by a newly isolated *Delftia tsuruhatensis* strain”.

Marijana Ponjavic (IMGGE) had a poster presentation titled “Conversion of mixed plastic waste containing PET into biopolymer bacterial nanocellulose”.

Diana Alicia Garza Herrera (TUS) had a poster presentation titled “Exploring the enzymatic ability of strains isolated from plastic polluted environments for enhancing synthetic and natural biopolymers’ biodegradation”.

Eduardo Lanzagorta Garcia (TUS) had a poster presentation titled “Biocompatible eco-plastic blends with enhanced antimicrobial activity by addition of essential oils”.

8. #RSCPoster 2024

#RSCPoster is a free global online poster conference organised annually by the Royal Society of Chemistry. The event, originally held on Twitter (now known as "X"), has moved to LinkedIn, which was held for 24 hours from 5-6 March 2024. In the previous edition, over 1500 delegates from 84 countries at every career stage shared their research and engaged in scientific debate.

Jeovan Araujo (TUS) had a poster presentation titled “Sustainable route for mixed (petro-bio)plastic waste valorisation via synergy-promoted enzymatic depolymerisation”.

9. 3Bs Materials International Conference

3Bs Materials 2024 Biomaterials, Biodegradables and Biomimetics International Conference, was organized jointly with the conferences Polymers 2024 International Conference and Composites 2024 International Conference. Research topics covered (a) Biomaterials, Biodegradables and Biomimetics, (b) Polymers and (c) Composites.

Filomena Freitas (NOVA) was the Keynote Speaker and delivered a presentation “Microbial polymers: novel biomaterials with improved properties”.

10. EFB virtual conference

The event gathered several field experts from academia and industry who delivered 13 inspiring keynote lectures, 13 oral communications, and several poster presentations throughout four engaging sessions on new bio-based plastics, biodegradation, plastic recycling, and environmental impact of discarded plastics that filled the day with knowledge-sharing and networking opportunities.

Jeovan Araujo (TUS) had a poster presentation titled “Biotechnological treatment of polyethylene terephthalate mixed plastic streams”.

11. 13th Congress of Microbiologists of Serbia

The aim of this event was to present the latest developments in microbiology that contribute to a better understanding of the role of microorganisms in nature. This regional meeting addressed all current microbiological problems and offered solutions to overcome them by world-class experts in the field.

Dusan Milivojevic (IMGGE) was an Invited Speaker and delivered a presentation “From soil to lab: Exploring toxicology with *Caenorhabditis elegans*”.

12. 6th Symposium of Biotransformations for Pharmaceutical and Cosmetic Industry

This conference was an excellent opportunity to meet representatives of academia, scientific institutions and industry and to discuss the latest trends in biotransformation processes, as well as prospects for the future in this field. The discussion covered many aspects of biotransformations, including the pharmaceutical, cosmetic, chemical and food industries. As in the previous editions, the scope of the conference was expanded by biotransformations in environmental protection.

Sandra Vojnovic (IMGGE) was an Invited Speaker and delivered a presentation “Biotransforming waste streams into biomolecules and biomaterials”.

3.3.3. Publications

During Y2, EcoPlastiC has produced and published 6 publications in international refereed journal that are listed in **Table 7**. They are deposited in the open repository Zenodo and are uploaded and accessible on the project website. The [EcoPlastiC community](#) was also created, and all publications that acknowledged EcoPlastiC can be found [here](#).

Table 7 – List of publications in Y2

Year	Title + Link	Journal	IF	Partner	Citation	Zenodo
2023	Exploring Microorganisms from Plastic-Polluted Sites: Unveiling Plastic Degradation and PHA Production Potential	Microorganisms	4.5	TUS IMGGE NOVA	Herrera, D.A.G.; Mojicevic, M.; Pantelic, B.; Joshi, A.; Collins, C.; Batista, M.; Torres, C.; Freitas, F.; Murray, P.; Nikodinovic-Runic, J.; et al. Exploring Microorganisms from Plastic-Polluted Sites: Unveiling Plastic Degradation and PHA Production Potential. <i>Microorganisms</i> 2023, 11, 2914. https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11122914	https://zenodo.org/record/13779495
2023	Boosting bacterial nanocellulose production from chemically recycled post-consumer polyethylene terephthalate	Sustainable Materials and Technologies	9.6	TUS NOVA	Da Silva Pereira, E.H.; Attallah, O.A.; Tas, C.E.; Chee, B.S.; Freitas, F.; Lanzagorta Garcia, E.; Mc Auliffe, M.A.P.; Mojicevic, M.; Batista, M.N.; Reis, M.A.M.; Brennan Fournet, M. Boosting bacterial nanocellulose production from chemically recycled post-consumer polyethylene terephthalate. <i>SM&T</i> 2024, 39, e00784. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susmat.2023.e00784	https://zenodo.org/record/13780045

2024	Biotechnological model for ubiquitous mixed petroleum- and bio-based plastics degradation and upcycling into bacterial nanocellulose	Journal of Cleaner Production	11.1	TUS IMGGE	Araujo, J.A.; Taxeidis, G.; Pereira, E.H.; Azeem, M.; Pantelic, B.; Jeremic, S.; Ponjavic, M.; Chen, Y.; Mojicevic, M.; Nikodinovic-Runic, J.; Topakas, E.; Brennan Fournet, M. Biotechnological model for ubiquitous mixed petroleum- and bio-based plastics degradation and upcycling into bacterial nanocellulose. J. Clean. Prod. 2024, 141025. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141025	https://zenodo.org/records/13780726
2024	Targeting bacterial nanocellulose properties through tailored downstream techniques	Polymers	5	TUS	Da Silva Pereira, E.H.; Mojicevic, M.; Tas, C.E.; Lanzagorta Garcia, E.; Brennan Fournet, M. Targeting Bacterial Nanocellulose Properties through Tailored Downstream Techniques. Polymers 2024, 16, 678. https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16050678	https://zenodo.org/records/13784626
2024	Unveiling the potential of bacterial isolates from plastic-polluted environments: enhancement of polyhydroxybutyrate biodegradation	Biotechnology for the Environment	NA	TUS	Herrera, D.A.G., Mojicevic, M., Venkatesh, C. et al. Unveiling the potential of bacterial isolates from plastic-polluted environments: enhancement of polyhydroxybutyrate biodegradation. Biotechnol Environ 1, 9 (2024). https://doi.org/10.1186/s44314-024-00009-y	https://zenodo.org/records/13784637

2024	Double layer bacterial nanocellulose e - poly(hydroxy octanoate) film activated by prodigiosin as sustainable, transparent, UV-blocking material	International Journal of Biological Macromolecules	7.7	IMGGE	Ivana Malagurski, Jelena Lazic, Tatjana Ilic-Tomic, Ana Salevic, Maciej Guzik, Marcel Krzan, Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic, Marijana Ponjavic, Double layer bacterial nanocellulose - poly(hydroxyoctanoate) film activated by prodigiosin as sustainable, transparent, UV-blocking material, Int. J. Biol. Macromolecules, 2024, 135087, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.135087	https://zenodo.org/record/13744832
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3.3.4. Media releases

EcoPlastiC project partners were hosted in 6 TV shows, 1 radio show and prepared 2 articles for online magazines and IMGGE as the leader of WP6 was particularly active in this respect. The list of media releases is shown in **Table 8** and short description are provided below **Table 8**.

Table 8 – List of articles and interviews given to the media

#	Partner institution	Type of media (name)	Presenters' name	Title and hyperlink
1	IMGGE	TV (RTS1)	Sanja Jeremic	Belgrade chronicles , from 31:45 (original title: "Beogradska hronika"), Topic: Microplastics
2	IMGGE	Radio (Radio Belgrade 1)	Sanja Jeremic	Magazine on the First , from 57:53 (original title: "Magazin na Prvom"), Topic: Microplastics - a threat to the survival of all life on earth
3	IMGGE	TV (K1, "Uranak")	Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic	How dangerous is plastic? (original title: "Koliko je plastika opasna?")
4	TUS	TV (RTS Nauka)	Marija Mojicevic	They (the women) , from 23:48 (original title: "One", show RTS Lab)
5	TUS	Online magazine (Priboj033)	Marija Mojicevic	Bacteria from the Priboj landfill are being researched by world scientists (Original title: Bakterije sa pribojske deponije istražuju svetski naučnici)
6	IMGGE	Blog, Science Technology Park	Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic	Commercialization of results from scientific works should be stimulated at different levels (original title: Komercijalizacija rezultata iz naučnih radova trebalo bi da bude stimulisana na različitim nivoima)

7	IMGGI	Online TV (Ekovizija)	Sanja Skaro Bogojevic	Eco Reportage - Bioplastics - 66 th International Fair of Technics and Technical Achievements
8	IMGGI	TV (RTS Nauka)	Sanja Skaro Bogojevic	M3 - Always more than a game from 14:16 (original title: “Uvek više od igre”, show RTS Lab)
9	IMGGE	Online TV (Ekovizija)	Jelena Milovanovic	Green studio: Microplastics (original title: “Zeleni studio”: Mikroplastika)

1. Belgrade chronicles on RTS1

Belgrade chronicles (Beogradska hronika) is a Serbian television program centred on events and current affairs concerning Belgrade, the country's capital. Reporters on the spot, current topics, important events, exclusive guests: this is what describes Belgrade chronicles, and Dr Sanja Jeremic (IMGGE) was invited to shed some light on the problem of plastic pollution.

2. Radio Belgrade 1 – Magazine on the First

Radio Belgrade 1 broadcasts a program live from Belgrade, Serbia. In addition to classical and pop music, Belgrade 1 internet radio broadcasts the well-known informative show “Magazine on the First”. Dr Sanja Jeremic was a guest there and she analysed the issue of plastics and offered solutions which are part of the EcoPlastiC project.

3. Early Morning Show on K1

Bringing the most important topics of the day, this vibrant morning show hosted our Team Leader of WP6 Dr Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic (IMGGE) as an expert on the topic of plastics where she introduced EcoPlastiC.

4. RTS Lab “They” on RTS SCIENCE

RTS SCIENCE (original: RTS NAUKA) is a TV channel devoted exclusively to scientific achievements of Serbian researchers. In this episode of the RTS Lab called “They (the women)”, several women and their research scopes were presented, as well as our Project Ambassador Dr Marija Mojicevic (TUS) and the EcoPlastiC project.

5. Priboj 033 online magazine

This online portal runs with the financial help of the EU as part of the “EU FOR YOU” initiative. Our project Ambassador Dr Marija Mojicevic (TUS) promoted the EcoPlastiC project and presented its goals and achievements to its readers.

NEW BLOG POST

6. Blog of the Science Technology Park

Science Technology Park Belgrade (STP Belgrade) supports start-ups and growing companies in the development and commercialisation of innovative products and services. With its activities, programs and services, STP Belgrade has a key impact in shaping the development of Serbia’s innovation ecosystem. Dr Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic (IMGGE) debated the potential for commercialisation of scientific results, as envisioned in the EcoPlastiC project.

7. Eco Reportage – Bioplastics on Eco Vision TV

At the International Fair of Technics and Technical Achievements, representatives from the IMGGE booth were selected among 904 exhibitors at this event to present into more details the ongoing projects, including the EcoPlastiC project. Dr Sanja Skaro Bogojevic was interviewed.

8. M3 – Always more than a game on RTS SCIENCE

As part of the ‘May Month of Mathematics (M3)’ a national manifestation organised since 2012, while 2024 theme was Biotechnology. The central exhibition included examples of biotechnology processes and tools, while Dr Sanja Skaro Bogojevic presented the EcoPlastiC project as a prime example of applied biotechnology for the improvement of everyday life.

9. “Green corner”: Microplastics

Jelena Milovanovic (IMGGE) participated in the “Green corner” show on Ekovizija (RTS Nauka), where the topic was microplastics! During the conversation, Jelena shared insights about our work in the EcoPlastiC project.

3.3.5 Education and public engagement at partners’ institutes

During Y2 of the project, AVE, IMGGE and TUS organised and participated in public engagement visits and manifestations. The list of these activities is shown in **Table 9** and short description are provided below **Table 9**.

Table 9 – List of activities focusing on education and public engagement

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
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Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe EIC Pathfinder programme under grant agreement No 101046758.

European Innovation Council

1	Company visit	AVE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	18/04/2024	Ghent, Belgium	30
2	Science Day	IMGGE	Exhibitors	EcoPlastiC project	13/07/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	150
3	Applied Polymer Technologies (APT) Facility opening	TUS	Participant	N.A.	20/09/2024	Athlone, Ireland	200

1. Avecom company visit

A group of 30 students from Ghent University (Faculty of Bioscience Engineering) visited AVE on 18/04/2024 in Ghent, Belgium. The visit started with a presentation of AVE followed by a tour in the company and a short introduction of the EcoPlastiC project by the Project Ambassador Helena Koninckx (AVE).

2. Science Day in Belgrade

The Science Day in Belgrade, Serbia was organised on 13/07/2024 and is conceived as a manifestation in honour of the birth of Nikola Tesla under the auspices of the Center for Scientific Research of Students of the Faculty of Biology. The idea of the event is to bring together the scientific achievements of research groups and student sections. From the IMGGE team, Dr Jelena Lazic, Dr Ivana Aleksic, Vukasin Jankovic, Dr Brana Pantelic, Dr Dusan Milivojevic were present to introduce the EcoPlastiC project to more than 150 visitors under the topic “Innovative waste quest: Can bacteria clean the rest?”. Additionally, Dr Brana Pantelic also delivered an inspiring talk “Biotechnological degradation of plastic waste” which involved the promotion of the EcoPlastiC project to the public.

3. Applied Polymer Technologies (APT) facility opening

The new state-of-the-art APT Facility at TUS is set to transform Ireland’s polymer and MedTech industries. The new facility reinforces the centre’s role as a crucial resource for national industries engaged in polymer research, innovation, and product development. APT was established to directly address the requirements of the polymer industry by training expert researchers and providing innovative solutions.

3.3.6 School visits

During Y2 of the project, numerous school visits were organised and the concepts of biodegradable plastics, biopolymers, upcycling and other were explained. The list of school visits is shown in **Table 10** and short description are provided below **Table 10**.

Table 10 – List of school visits where the EcoPlastiC project was presented.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	ERN: Researchers at schools	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	16/11/2023	Uzice, Serbia	95
2	ERN: Researchers at schools	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	11/12/2023	Veliko Gradiste, Srbija	45
3	ERN: Researchers at schools	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	07/02/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	35
4	ERN: Researchers at schools	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	22/02/2024	Backa Topola, Serbia	70
5	ERN: Researchers at schools	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	23/02/2024	Smederevska Palanka, Serbia	30
6	Engineers Week 2024 at St. Comán's Wood Primary School	TUS	Presenter	New Plastics for a New Generation	02/03/2024	Roscommon, Ireland	22
7	ToyStories	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	11/04/2024	Athlone, Ireland	30
8	ToyStories	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	28/05/2024	Athlone, Ireland	15
9	ToyStories	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	28/05/2024	Novi Sad, Serbia	26
10	ToyStories	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	31/05/2024	Kragujevac, Serbia	22
11	ToyStories	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	07/06/2024	Pozarevac, Serbia	21
12	ToyStories	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	07/06/2024	Vranje, Serbia	24
13	ToyStories	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	12/09/2024	Longford, Ireland	78
14	ToyStories	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	19/09/2024	Roscommon, Ireland	45
15	ToyStories	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	26/09/2024	Dublin, Ireland	22
16	ToyStories	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	30/09/2024	Cork, Ireland	57

1-5. European researchers' Night: Researchers at schools

IMGGE organised the activity "Researchers at schools" as part of the European Researchers' Night (ERN) project funded by the European Commission. All secondary schools in Serbia were invited to host young scientists who presented their projects from various fields of research.

The IMGGE representatives presented the EcoPlastiC project in:

16/11/2023 in Uzice (Dr Jelena Lazic and Dr Ivana Aleksic) to 95 high school students

11/12/2023 in Veliko Gradiste (Brana Pantelic and Vukasin Jankovic) to 45 high school students

07/02/2024 in Belgrade (Dr Marijana Ponjavic and Vukasin Jankovic) to 35 high school students

22/02/2024 in Backa Topola (Dr Jelena Lazic and Dr Ivana Aleksic) to 70 high school students

23/02/2024 in Smederevska Palanka (Dr Dusan Milivojevic, Brana Pantelic, Vukasin Jankovic) to 30 high school students

6. Engineers Week 2024

Engineers Week is a fantastic opportunity to promote engineering within the primary school and help pupils to have a better understanding of the impact of engineering in everyday life. BioICEP and EcoPlastiC projects were presented by Jeovan Araujo at St. Comán's Wood Primary School in Roscommon. The 22 pupils demonstrated a great understanding of sustainability for plastics, giving examples of sustainable practices carried out at the school, which are organized by the internal Green School committee.

7-14. ToyStories

The project ToyStories aims to investigate and improve current knowledge of children and young people on the state of plastic pollution and sustainable solutions. The main goal of this project is to raise awareness, empower and teach young people how to adapt and act on worldwide issue such as plastic pollution. The project was clustered with EcoPlastiC and several visits in Ireland and Serbia were organised where after the ToyStories activities, the importance of the EcoPlastiC project was explained to the pupils:

Ireland:

11/04/2024 in Athlone (Dr Marija Mojicevic and Dr Eduardo Lanzagorta Garcia) for 30 pupils

12/09/2024 in Longford (Dr. Eduardo Lanzagorta Garcia and Henrique Pereira) for 78 pupils

19/09/2024 in Roscommon (Dr. Eduardo Lanzagorta Garcia and Henrique Pereira) for 45 pupils

26/09/2024 in Dublin (Dr. Eduardo Lanzagorta Garcia and Henrique Pereira) for 22 pupils

30/09/2024 in Cork (Dr. Eduardo Lanzagorta Garcia and Henrique Pereira) for 57 pupils

Serbia:

28/08/2024 in Novi Sad (Vukasin Jankovic and Sara Petrovic) for 26 pupils

31/05/2024 in Kragujevac (Dr Jelena Lazic and Dr Sandra Vojnovic) for 22 pupils

07/06/2024 in Pozarevac (Dr Ivana Aleksic) for 21 pupils

07/06/2024 in Vranje (Vukasin Jankovic, Brana Pantelic) for 24 pupils

3.3.7 Women in Science events

During Y2, one event was attended by female team members from IMGGE (**Table 11**) and its details are shown below **Table 11**.

Table 11 – List of Women in Science events from Y2.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	Belgrade Business Run 2024	IMGGE	Participant	Women Run Science - EcoPlastiC project	26/09/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	9300 runners

1. Belgrade Business Run 2024

During the Belgrade Business Run of 5 km, the all-female IMGGE team collected plastic waste and after the run, they organised an exhibition of the collected materials and introduced the EcoPlastiC project to other participants of the race. They emphasised the role of women and girls in science and promoted the EcoPlastiC project and its achievements. With 9300 participants and 600 cheerleaders from 450 companies in Belgrade, this activity resulted in great interest.

3.3.8 Special sessions, forums and events organised by other EU Research Projects

EcoPlastiC is actively engaged in collaborative clustering activities and establishing strong connections with other relevant EU research projects and initiatives. This collaborative approach is particularly significant given that several consortium members are already involved in various EU-funded projects. By fostering these relationships, EcoPlastiC ensures cross-project synergy, facilitates knowledge exchange, and enhances the overall impact of its research efforts across

the European innovation landscape. The strategic involvement with these projects allows for the sharing of best practices, resources, and insights, further strengthening EcoPlastiC's role within the broader EU research community.

EcoPlastiC is actively participating in clustering activities and collaborating with other relevant EU research projects and initiatives, which is shown in **Table 12**. This is particularly important as several consortium members are also involved in other EU-funded projects.

Table 12 – List of events organised by other EU-funded projects during Y2 where the EcoPlastiC project was presented.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	PFAStwin webinar	IMGGE	Presenter	Microplastic – a macroscopic problem	14/03/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	40
2	BioICEP Final Event	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	16/05/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	80
3	TwInn4MicroUp Kick-off Meeting	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	12-13/09/2024	Athens, Greece	25

1. PFAStwin webinar

This was one in a cycle of lectures „ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION - FROM CONSCIOUS TO UNCONSCIOUS“ organised by the Faculty of Chemistry, the Environmental Chemistry Section of the Serbian Chemical Society and the PFAStwin project. Dr Jasmine Nikodinovic-Runic (IMGGE) delivered a talk titled “[Microplastics – a macroscopic problem](#)” during which the EcoPlastiC project was presented.

2. BioICEP Final Event

EU-funded Horizon 2020 BioICEP project (Bio Innovation of a Circular Economy for Plastics) organised a ceremonial event marking the completion of the project. This event was focused around the topic "Advancing Plastics Circular Economy: A Leap Forward in Closing the Loop" and was attended by more than 80 registered participants. Dr Margaret Brennan Fournet (TUS) presented the EcoPlastiC project to the participants.

3. TwInn4MicroUp Kick-off Meeting

At the kick-off meeting of the [TwInn4MicroUp](#) - **Twinning Innovation Hub for Microbial Platforms in Plastic Upcycling**, the EcoPlastiC Project Ambassador Jelena Lazic (IMGGE) was invited to present the *EcoPlastiC Work Package 6 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication*, and to enable knowledge transfer to the TwInn4MicroUp consortium members, especially related to the *TwInn4MicroUp Work Package 6 – Outreach, Communication and Dissemination*.

4. Indicators and targets - summary

Table 13 – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and targets

Channel/ Activity	Target number	Y1	Y2	Total
Website	Visits per year: <500 poor; 500-1000 good; >1000 excellent	1700 unique visitors	3600 unique visitors	
Twitter	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	169 followers	356 followers	
LinkedIn	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	104 followers	362 followers	
Facebook	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	24 followers + 15 likes	38 followers + 19 likes	
Instagram	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	166 followers	280 followers	
Events	Attendances: <5 poor; 5-7 good; >7 excellent	7 events attended	14 events attended	21
Conferences	Attendances: <4 poor; 4-6 good; >6 excellent	6 conferences attended	12 conferences attended	18
Publications	Published articles: <5 poor; 5-10 good; >10 excellent	1 publication	6 publications	7
Media releases	Media: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	5 media releases	9 media releases	14

Education and public engagement at partners' institutes	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	0	3 lectures/visits	3
School visits	Visits: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	0	16 visits	16
Women in science events	Attendances: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	0	1	1
Special sessions, forums, events organised by other EU Research Initiatives	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	1 visit	3 visits	4

From the 13 channels and activities, there are 8 that are performing with 'excellent' KPIs, which is expected at the end of Y2.

A total of 3 channels/activities are performing with 'good' KPIs. As the project progresses and novel results are generated, we are confident that the number of publications will come up to the 'excellent' category and that the final number of publications at the end of Y3 will be >10. In addition, the partners plan more education and public engagement activities at partners' institutes in Y3. Finally, we also expect that EcoPlastiC partners will be invited to participate in several other events organised by other EU Research Initiatives, and that the final KPI for this category in Y3 will also shift to 'excellent'.

There are 2 channels/activities that are in the 'poor' category. The number of followers on Facebook remains low, but this is due to the fact this social medium has lost its momentum and is not as popular as in the previous decade. Our focus in Y3 of the project will be on the Women in Science events and we will strive to organise and/or participate in >4 events in Y3.

5. Exploitation of the key project results

The EcoPlastiC project holds significant potential for exploitation of its results, not only by advancing scientific knowledge and its dissemination, but also by commercially capitalising on the EcoPlastiC innovation. To achieve this, a robust exploitation plan must be implemented, including appropriate activities and measures throughout the project's duration.

The initial concept of the exploitation plan was presented in the first version of DEC Plan delivered in M6 and the updated plan and presentation of the progress in the first year of project implementation was presented in M12. Based on the project proposal of the EcoPlastiC project, the project partners have previously defined the following key exploitable results (KERs) shown and explained in **Table 14**, with responsible partners and IP owners for each KER.

Table 14. EcoPlastiC Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

Key Exploitable Results (KERs)	Interest/Description	WPs	Responsible partner	IP owner(s)
KER1 – Green depolymerisation into constituent monomers as a new generation technology	To convert lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste to efficient polymer monomer and multimer fermentable feedstock for biopolymers and Eco-plastics by stream production processes from difficult to recycle post-use PET packaging and textile plastics.	WP2	TUS	TUS
KER2 – Enhanced and optimized Avecom microbiomes	To generate a value-added PHA biopolymer and other useful products by degradation and bioconversion of fermentable feedstock of waste plastic monomers and multimers.	WP3	AVE	AVE
KER3 – Prototype PHA biopolymer materials	To develop and validate new PHA biopolymer materials focused on PHA, PHA3HV and other high performance copolymers, with performance properties equivalent to petroleum counterpart plastics, and extruded as potential future packaging plastics.	WP4	NOVA	NOVA, AVE, IMGGE
KER4 – Small-scale demonstrators of food packaging applications	To demonstrate EcoPlastiC innovation (new generation of recycling technology) to plastic value chain companies to produce high potential sustainable plastic products (by profile extrusion, blown film extrusion, thermoforming and injection moulding, cast film and vacuum forming).	WP5	KTH, TUS	KTH

Main elements of exploitation strategy and appropriate measures to be implemented are structured for each key exploitable results as follows:

- Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description
- **Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation**
- Technical innovation (short description)
- Main competitive advantage(s)
- **KER protection (IPR measures)**
- **Target sector(s)**
- **Early adopters**
- **Target users**
- **Primary market**
- **Market barriers**
- **Communication & dissemination measures**
- Expected impact
- **Further steps to scaling-up**

Updated individual exploitation strategies for KERs are presented in Annex I of this Report. Some of the elements of the strategy are interesting for monitoring and reporting during the project (written in **bold** font), so in Table A1 are summarized progress for key results related to the already presented dissemination and communication measures implemented during the second year of the project.

Table 15. KER1 exploitation progress (responsible TUS)

KER1	Green depolymerisation into constituent monomers as a new generation technology	Progress in the second year <i>(short description and measurable indicators)</i>
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	Preparation For Spin out with entrepreneurship team identified and business plan completed.	In partnership with the Novelplast , the scale-up process began in Year 1, and initial results indicate its success. The TPA monomer has been produced at high yields from a number of waste PET streams including coloured PET/PE and metallised PET. Additionally, collaboration interest with ALPEK has been identified.
KER protection (IPR measures)	Patent application.	UK Patent Application No: 2116474.4.

		International Patent Application No: PCT/EP2022/082101.
Target sector(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plastic/plastic waste producing industries • Packaging industries • Waste treatment industries 	Leading producer of PTA & PET has been targeted in Year 1.
Early adopters	ALPEK polyesters, NOVELPLAST, Avaencourt	Scale up experiments have been successfully conducted at Krauss Maffie and further investment is required to progress to the next stage
Target users/Primary market	Plastic producing companies/Packaging companies/Waste treatment facilities	New collaboration with ALPEK is being explored.
Market barriers	Technological readiness TRL6	Actively working with NovelPlast and Avoncourt to secure investment to deliver scaled up operation.
Communication & dissemination measures	<p>Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events.</p> <p>Encourage on-going two-way dialogue between the consortium and industry stakeholders.</p>	<p>TUS Research week (poster presentation). Presentation to TUS company clients.</p> <p>Margaret Brennan Fournet, visited Eli Lilly at their Limerick facility. Eli Lilly announced a significant expansion of their manufacturing operations, with a €1 billion investment in Ireland aimed at increasing the production of biologic active ingredients for global disease treatment—an important focus area for LIFE RI. Margaret Brennan Fournet spoke with the Mayor of Limerick, John Moran, and Kieran O'Donnell TD, Minister of State for the Office of Public Works, about the collaborative work undertaken across TUS</p>

		research, development, and LIFE RI.
Further steps to scaling-up	Current TRL: 4-5 at the end of the project's Year 1. Expected TRL: 6-7, towards the end of the project.	Current TRL: 4-5

KER1A	High Gas barrier packaging¹ (a least equivalent to petro-based Ethylene vinyl alcohol (EVOH))	Progress in the second year <i>(short description and measurable indicators)</i>
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	KTH and TUS are actively developing High Gas barrier packaging (a least equivalent to petro-based Ethylene vinyl alcohol (EVOH) O ₂ barrier 0.4 [cm ² .mm/(m ² .24h.atm)]), using microbial protein (MP) and polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) layered films and trays	Layered films and trays identified for prototype developments including supermarket precooked food, bag-in-box wines and other beverages, dairy products/cheese, bake-up bread and meat products such as trays and film wrapping for meat maturation (The layered structure enabling use as translucent packaging for UV-sensitive food products.
KER protection (IPR measures)	Know-How and In-house Microbial Strains	Newly validated for high performance barrier properties combined with full circularity and high potential LCA metrics
Target sector(s)	Food Packaging value chain and related stakeholders	/
Early adopters	Meat industry, Supermarket Food suppliers	Potential being explored with companies such as Zeus Packaging, LogoPlaste, TetraPack, Dawn Meats, Lactips Amcor and Kerry Group

¹ <https://innovation-radar.ec.europa.eu/innovation/54123>

Target users/Primary market	Food Packaging value chain and related stakeholders	Zeus Packaging, LogoPlaste, TetraPack, Dawn Meats, Lactips Amcor and Kerry Group
Market barriers	Bio-refineriss are emerging and are not yet widely available	Submitted EIC Transition proposal for Scale up to bring to TRL 6-7 (see Table A4 in Annex I for more details).
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events.	TUS Research week (poster presentation). Presentation to TUS company clients
Further steps to scaling-up	Current TRL: 4-5, towards the end of the project's Year 3.	Current TRL: 4

KER1B	Bioadhesives for paper cups and plastic packaging sealant prototypes with equivalent performance to conventional synthetic adhesives.	Progress in the second year (<i>short description and measurable indicators</i>)
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	TUS are actively developing Bioadhesives with adhesion values approaching commercial Prittstick and Superglue.	Bioadhesives for paper & plastic packaging sealant prototypes using enhanced MP
KER protection (IPR measures)	Know-How and In-house Microbial Strains	Newly validated for high performance adhesion combined with full circularity and high potential LCA metrics
Target sector(s)	Food Packaging value chain and related stakeholders	/
Early adopters	Meat industry, Supermarket Food suppliers	Potential being explored with companies such as Zeus Packaging, LogoPlaste, TetraPack, Dawn Meats, Lactips Amcor and Kerry Group

Target users/Primary market	Food Packaging value chain and related stakeholders	Zeus Packaging, LogoPlaste, TetraPack, Dawn Meats, Lactips Amcor and Kerry Group
Market barriers	Biorefineries are emerging and are not yet widely available	Submitted EIC Transition proposal for Scale up to bring to TRL 6-7
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events.	TUS Research week (poster presentation). Presentation to TUS company clients
Further steps to scaling-up	Current TRL: 4-5, towards the end of the project's Year 3.	Current TRL: 4

Table 16. KER2 exploitation progress (responsible AVE)

KER2	Enhanced and optimized Avecom microbiomes	Progress in the second year (short description and measurable indicators)
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	AVE will disseminate the exploitable outputs of EcoPlastiC project by participating in industry events and conferences where there is potential to network, hold exhibition stands, to secure further collaborations, research contracts, or licensing deals.	AVE hosted a webinar in which EcoPlastiC was represented
KER protection (IPR measures)	No patent application is planned. The results will be protected by trade secret.	All obtained results are confidential (know-how secret).
Target sector(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste treatment industries PHA producing companies Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive 	The developed technology can be exploited by packaging companies and waste treatment industries.
Early adopters	Waste collecting industries: they could use this technology not only to recycle plastic but to valorize and upgrade their plastic waste to a raw material that can be used for the production of valuable products or possibly a eco-plastics.	Waste collecting industries can apply the anaerobic conversion of pretreated PET into biogas.

Target users/Primary market	<p>The following potential customers were identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solid Waste treatment / collecting utilities operators (domestic / industrial general waste). • Plastic recycling operators (domestic / industrial sorted waste). • Plastic industry (scraps waste, monomer(s) waste, etc). • Industries generating plastic waste (treating waste in situ). • Packaging industry 	<p>In order to reach potential customers, AVE had handed out the Ecoplastic flyer at Aquarama</p> <p>The second newsletter was shared on the Ave website.</p>
Market barriers	Production cost, Technological readiness	<p>The conversion speed of the anaerobic culture.</p> <p>Mixed culture has the potential of reducing the production cost.</p>
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events, organising visits for potential investors and/or B2B to the demo plant	AVE hosted a webinar in which EcoPlastiC was represented
Further steps to scaling-up	<p>At the end of EcoPlastiC project, it is estimated to reach TRL3-4. If successful, it can be estimated to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years. TRL6-7 could be achieved after another 2-4 years. Thus, the time to market could be between 7-10 years.</p>	AVE is in the optimisation of TRL2/3 and is assumed to reach TRL3/4 as planned.

Table 17. KER3 exploitation progress (responsible NOVA, IMGGE)

KER3	Prototype PHA biopolymer materials	Progress in the second year (<i>short description and measurable indicators</i>)
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	NOVA will disseminate the exploitable outputs of EcoPlastiC project by participating in conferences where there is potential to network, to secure further	<p>NOVA participated in two conferences (Mikrobiokosmos 2023 and 3Bs Materials 2024).</p> <p>A new research European project, UPSTREAM (GA: 101112877), was initiated where NOVA will collaborate with VITO (Belgium), Tecnopackaging (Spain) and the National Institute of Chemistry (Slovenia) in the</p>

	<p>collaborations and new research contracts. IMGGE will also disseminate through scientific publications and conferences and direct contact with commercial stakeholders.</p>	<p>production of PHA from plastics recovered from rivers. NOVA also participated in two proposals: ME4BIO coordinated by the Universidad de Alicante (Spain) submitted to the HORIZON-CL6-2024-CIRCBIO-01 call; and BIO2VALUE, coordinated by the ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION (Greece) submitted to the HORIZON-CL6-2024-CircBio-02-6-two-stage - From silos to diversity – small-scale bio-based demonstration pilots call. For these projects/proposals, the know-how of PHA production and plastic biodegradation obtained by NOVA in the EcoPlastiC project was essential.</p> <p>At IMGGE, 3 new PHA-based blends were prepared at IMGGE. One of the blends was already published in “Double layer bacterial nanocellulose - poly(hydroxyoctanoate) film activated by prodigiosin as sustainable, transparent, UV-blocking material” (https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.135087), and 2 other blends with enhanced properties, including one on the base of bio-polyurethane, are being evaluated as novel materials.</p>
KER protection (IPR measures)	No patent application is planned. The results will be protected by trade secret.	
Target sector(s)	PHA producing companies Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive sectors	
Early adopters	Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive sectors	
Target users/Primary market	Packaging Industry	

Market barriers	Production cost, Technological readiness	
Communication & dissemination measures	<p>Conferences, peer-reviewed scientific journals, social media, workshops and fairs.</p> <p>Organising visits for potential investors and/or B2B to the demo plant.</p>	<p>IMGGE organised meetings with several companies:</p> <p><u>SPEKTAR</u> https://www.spektar.com/</p> <p>SPEKTAR company is one of a leading food packaging companies in Serbia, with more than 90 % of products the production exported in the USA market. The main company activity is processing and sales of multilayer polyamide sausage casings and high barrier heat-shrinkable films and bags, which are used in the food-processing industry for packaging of meat and dairy products. In front of the company, deputy director Olivera Matovic, hosted two of the IMGGE team members. During the meeting, both sides had the opportunity to present their works, and the collaboration and participation in the Science Excellence Hub (Horizon call) consortium had been established. The IMGGE team visited the whole company, all departments, from R&D, quality control laboratory, to production and sales. The collaboration with SPEKTAR company will be continued.</p> <p><u>TetraPak</u> https://www.tetrapak.com/en-rs</p> <p>Tetra Pak is the world's leading food processing and packaging solutions company working closely with our customers and suppliers to provide safe food. The global Tetra Pak organisation consists of 100 sales offices, 27 market companies and 51 production plants, with 6 R&D centers, 7 Customer Innovation Centers and 8 Training Centers. As a Tetra Pak company representative (branch in Belgrade, Serbia), Ms Tanja Basta, Sustainability Expert for East Europe, Tetra Pak Production, visited IMGGE and presented the Tetra Pak recycling</p>

	<p>solutions, collection of waste and end-of use life for the packaging materials from their assortment. The meeting was also an excellent opportunity for the IMGGE EcoPlastiC team to introduce the project ideas and perspectives, to share the ideas for the potential projects in the future and to discuss about potential collaborations.</p> <p><u><i>Esensa - Nature and Health</i></u> https://www.esensa.rs/en/</p> <p>ESENSA is a Serbian company that produces dietary supplements, medical devices and cosmetics and biocidal products. The company covers the markets of Serbia, Montenegro, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Macedonia and in over 40 other countries around the world including. The main production capacities include different pharmaceutical forms (solid forms: tablets, capsules, powders, semisolid forms: ointments, creams, gels, liquid forms: syrups, solutions, aerosols, liquid monodose packs). ESENSA company expresses the great interest for the collaboration that further resulted in the participation in project consortium (Science Excellence Hub (Horizon call)). The company representatives recognized the potential of being industrial representative in the project as an end-user of new sustainable packaging material for their products that can be evaluated and tested by them satisfying all standard tests required for the pharmaceutical formulations packaging.</p> <p><u>BioCombact - Sustainable Agriculture Technologies</u> https://combact.rs/</p> <p>BioCombact - Dedicated Biotech Developers and Experts - is young company that develop and commercialising an innovative bio-based fertilizers. The biggest challenge of BioCombact is formulating a set of</p>
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		<p>environmentally friendly and healthcare-safe bio-based mixtures, to act as a highly efficient bio-fertilisers with pesticide characteristics. The company activity covers Microbiome analysis, biotech R&D and microbial fertilizers development to support sustainable agriculture. The collaboration between BioCombact and IMGGE has been accomplished through the participation in the consortium for project application. BioCombact has expressed interest to test EcoPlastiC materials for biodegradation in natural environments.</p> <p><u>FOKA</u> https://foka.rs/en/</p> <p>FOKA company, as a leader in the production of packaging in Serbia, primarily in food industry, has been recognized as potential partner for future projects. This Serbian company produces 1,200 different materials adapted to more than 16,000 packaging solutions, including PBL tubes with and without an EVOH layer, recyclable, high-barrier thermoforming foils (FokaBAR TF 150 and FokaTOP 77). The company was contacted, and after the IMGGE team presented the current projects and future perspectives, the management of FOKA company expressed their interest for collaboration and participation in future project calls.</p>
Further steps to scaling-up	<p>At the end of EcoPlastiC project, it is estimated to reach TRL3-4. If successful, it can be estimated to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years. TRL6-7 could be achieved after another 2-4 years. Thus, the time to market could be between 7-10 years.</p>	

Table 18. KER4 exploitation progress (responsible KTH)

KER4	Small-scale demonstrators of food packaging applications	Progress in the second year (short description and measurable indicators)
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	KTH will lead the development of high-performance eco-plastics blends and single/multilayers for food packaging applications (flexible packaging and trays). Replacement of fossil-based plastics into PHA enriched eco-plastics and microbial/single-cell bio-plastics.	WP5 starts at M24 and the progress regarding demonstrators for food packaging applications will be described in the following reporting periods.
KER protection (IPR measures)	The outcome results will be discussed within the consortium and published in scientific journals. If any breakthrough results find, that may be patented.	No patent-filing currently. Three publications are planned and two are under writing
Target sector(s)	Plastic producers, packaging companies in the food sector, food producers and retailers	
Early adopters	Food packaging industries could be in the first row to adopt our eco-friendly biopolymer as alternative to fossil-based plastics.	
Target users/Primary market	Packaging producers, food producers and retailers	
Market barriers	Food packaging approval, logistics	
Communication & dissemination measures	International conference participation, Laboratory tours to design smart equipment, webinar talks to enhance the network in packaging sector, motivate youth towards the eco-friendly science projects by showcasing our new eco-plastic prototype products. Publication in scientific journals.	We have had communications with Graphic Packaging International and Tetra Pak on SCP/PHA materials. Publications planned for SCP films/trays, SCP/biopolymer blends and multilayer films. No organized visits for potential investors planned currently.
Further steps to scaling-up	At the end of EcoPlastiC project, it is estimated we reach TRL3-4.	

	<p>If successful, it can be estimated to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years.</p> <p>Based on the results from the EcoPlastiC project, a HORIZON-EIC-2024-TRANSITION-01 project application (EcoPACK) is being prepared. To increase the production of industry steered prototype production, high adoption and uptake rates of sustainable technologies, actively engaging with plastic value chain industries is central to the EcoPACK project serving to empower companies to achieve circularity for their products and processes.</p>	
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6. Conclusions

This report **D6.7** provides an overview of the dissemination, exploitation and communication work carried out in the second year on the EcoPlastiC project, from 1st October 2023 – 30th September 2024. It summaries the main activities of all partners, which were systematically organised and presented by IMGGE, the project partner leading WP6 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication. It is based on the detailed **D6.1** Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (M6), which provided a framework to communicate our project activities and disseminate project results, and it is a continuation of the **D6.3** First annual report on Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities.

During Y2, EcoPlastiC project partners participated at 14 events, 12 conferences, they published 6 papers, had 9 media releases, organised a total of 3 education and public engagements, 14 school visits, participated in one women in science event and were invited to take part in 3 events organised by other EU research initiatives.

Furthermore, during Y2, additional dissemination materials were prepared, including bookmarks, notepads, folders and ballpoint pens. EcoPlastiC website was improved and the search for specific events and downloadable materials was made possible. The EcoPlastiC Newsletter #2 campaign was sent out.

ANNEX I – KER market-oriented exploitation progress

This part of the DEC Plan will be regularly updated by EcoPlastiC partners.

Table A1. KER1 Market-oriented exploitation approach (responsible TUS)

KER1	Green depolymerisation into constituent monomers as a new generation technology
Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description	Mechano-green strategies developed at TUS aim to combine a range of polymer treatments (ultrasonication, UV degradation, microwave treatment and reactive extrusion) to close the loop of mixed plastic waste management by allowing the depolymerization of materials to source new monomers for the production of virgin PET and produce the feedstock for the manufacture of new biobased and biodegradable materials. Outcomes will be disseminated through conferences, scientific publications, reports, and social media channels. Patent regarding this technology has been submitted.
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	Further optimisation and upgrading of existing technology will be conducted at TUS. Communication with industry sector and other research facilities in order to up-scale and boost efficiency of the process will be implemented.
Technical innovation (short description)	<p>A method for processing polyester plastic waste material, such as post-consumer polyethylene terephthalate waste material, using hot-melt extrusion of the plastic waste material in the presence of a depolymerisation agent and a plasticising agent comprising one or more inorganic salts.</p> <p>UK Patent Application No: 2116474.4. International Patent Application No: PCT/EP2022/082101.</p>
Main competitive advantage(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a continuous recycling technology for all grades of PET – spanning pristine bottle grades to low grade PET pots and trays. • Significant contribution towards halting resource depletion, landfilling and incineration of waste plastics instead converting them into valuable resources and demonstrating the implementation of a circular plastic model.
KER protection (IPR measures)	As mentioned before, part of this research is already in the process of Patent submission.

Target sector(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plastic/plastic waste producing industries • Packaging industries • Waste treatment industries
Early adopters	ALPEK polyesters, NOVELPLAST, Avencourt
Target users/Primary market	Plastic producing companies/Packaging companies/Waste treatment facilities
Market barriers	Technological readiness
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events.
Expected impact	Making a substantial impact in the effort to combat resource depletion, reduce the disposal of plastics in landfills and incineration, and instead, transforming waste plastics into valuable resources while showcasing the practical application of a circular plastic economy.
Further steps to scaling-up	Current TRL: 4-5, towards the end of the project's Y1. Expected TRL: 6-7, towards the end of the project.

Table A2. KER2 Market-oriented exploitation approach (responsible AVE)

KER2	Enhanced and optimized AVE microbiomes
Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description	The knowledge generated on optimization of microbiomes and production of biopolymer would be disseminated to scientific community, industry sector, government, environmental NGOs and civil society of progress that is being made in the field of environmental monitoring. The key parameters of the pilot - process parameters, scientific and technical know-how, design, maintenance, production and engineering - of the technology for the production of the bio-product will be protected as a trade secret. Exploitation intentions are either manufacturing a bioproduct, either licensing to industry.
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	AVE will disseminate the exploitable outputs of EcoPlastiC project by participating in industry events and conferences where there is potential to network, hold exhibition stands, to secure further collaborations, research contracts, or licensing deals.

Technical innovation (short description)	The result of the project will be a solution for mixed plastic pollution. ECOPLASTIC converts lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste into high performing biopolymers, through the development of a suite of breakthrough modular and technologies adaptable to the waste input and provides next generation technology to funnel waste PET plastics into Eco-products.
Main competitive advantage(s)	In case bio-plastic production is possible, this KER will become a key to turn a linear process of plastic into a circular economy.
KER protection (IPR measures)	No patent application is planned. The results will be protected by trade secret.
Target sector(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste treatment industries • PHA producing companies • Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive
Early adopters	Waste collecting industries: they could use this technology not only to recycle plastic but to valorize and upgrade their plastic waste to a raw material that can be used for the production of valuable products or possibly a eco-plastics.
Target users/Primary market	The following potential customers were identified: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solid Waste treatment / collecting utilities operators (domestic / industrial general waste). • Plastic recycling operators (domestic / industrial sorted waste). • Plastic industry (scraps waste, monomer(s) waste, etc). • Industries generating plastic waste (treating waste in situ). • Packaging industry
Market barriers	Production cost, Technological readiness
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events, organising visits for potential investors and/or B2B to the demo plant
Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • less (micro) plastic might contaminate soil/water and newer biodegradable plastic would naturally decompose. • it is expected that the CO2 emissions of the newer biodegradable plastic would be lower.

Further steps to scaling-up	<p>At the end of EcoPlastiC project, it is estimated to reach TRL3-4.</p> <p>If successful, it can be estimated to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years.</p> <p>TRL6-7 could be achieved after another 2-4 years.</p> <p>Thus, the time to market could be between 7-10 years.</p>
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Table A3. KER3 Market-oriented exploitation approach (responsible NOVA, IMGGE)

KER3	Prototype PHA biopolymer materials
Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description	The knowledge generated on PHA biopolymer materials will be disseminated to scientific community and plastic industry sector. The scientific and technical know-how will be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals or protected as a trade secret. Exploitation intentions are licensing to industry.
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	NOVA will disseminate the exploitable outputs of EcoPlastiC project by participating in conferences where there is potential to network, to secure further collaborations and new research contracts.
Technical innovation (short description)	PHA biopolymer materials focused on PHB, PHBHV and other high performance copolymers, with performance properties equivalent to petroleum counterpart plastics, and extruded as potential future packaging plastics.
Main competitive advantage(s)	PHA biopolymer materials
KER protection (IPR measures)	No patent application is planned. The results will be protected by trade secret.
Target sector(s)	PHA producing companies Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive
Early adopters	Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive
Target users/Primary market	Packaging Industry
Market barriers	Production cost, Technological readiness
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, peer-reviewed scientific journals, social media, workshops and fairs.
Expected impact	less (micro) plastic might contaminate soil/water and newer biodegradable plastic would naturally decompose. it is expected that the CO2 emissions of the newer biodegradable plastic would be lower.
Further steps to scaling-up	At the end of EcoPlastiC project, it is estimated to reach TRL3-4.

	<p>If successful, it can be estimated to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years.</p> <p>TRL6-7 could be achieved after another 2-4 years.</p> <p>Thus, the time to market could be between 7-10 years.</p>
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Table A4. KER4 Market-oriented exploitation approach (responsible KTH, TUS)

KER4	Small-scale demonstrators of food packaging applications
Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description	High, the explanation is provided below.
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	KTH will lead the development of high-performance eco-plastics blends and single/multilayers (flexible packaging and trays) for food packaging applications. Replacement of fossil-based plastics into PHA enriched eco-plastics and microbial/single-cell bio-plastics.
Technical innovation (short description)	Producing bioplastics from PET waste
Main competitive advantage(s)	We know how to produce plastics from bio-sources
KER protection (IPR measures)	The outcome results will be discussed within the consortium and published in scientific journals. If any breakthrough results find, that may be patented.
Target sector(s)	Plastic producers, packaging companies in the food sector, food producers and retailers
Early adopters	Food packaging industries could be in the first row to adopt our eco-friendly biopolymer as alternative to fossil-based plastics.
Target users/Primary market	Plastics producers, Packaging producers, Recycling sector in Plastics, Food producers and retailers
Market barriers	Food packaging approval, logistics
Communication & dissemination measures	International conference participation, Laboratory tours to design smart equipment, webinar talks to enhance the network in packaging sector, motivate youth towards the eco-friendly science projects by showcasing our new eco-plastic prototype products. Publications in scientific journals.
Expected impact	The plasticized PHA and Microbial protein biopolymers positively impacts on environment which could fulfil our environmental goals such as life-on-land, and life-below-water.

Further steps to scaling-up	At the end of EcoPlastiC project, it is estimated to reach TRL3-4. If successful, it can be estimated to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years.
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